

Professional Competence as Predictor of Teachers' Sense of Efficacy in Asuncion, Davao Del Norte

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Abstract. The current study examined the impact of professional competence on teachers' sense of efficacy. In this study, the researcher selected 185 elementary school teachers from the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte as the respondents. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the respondents. A non-experimental quantitative research design using a descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected to the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and regression analysis. Findings revealed that professional competence and sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte were described as extensive. Furthermore, correlation analysis revealed a significant relationship between professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. Evidently, regression analysis revealed that professional competence, in terms of environmental control and self-disclosure, was a significant predictor of teachers' sense of efficacy in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. It is therefore recommended that DepEd should allocate resources for ongoing, high-quality professional development programs that cater to the specific needs of teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational Management 2. Professional Competence 3. Sense of Efficacy 4. Teachers 5. Regression Analysis

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1. Introduction

Teachers' training is a commonly discussed subject in the country's educational agenda. The restructuring of education systems, caused by the constantly changing social structure, has brought new discussions and conflicts. Considering the problems related to the teaching profession, it is essential to focus on the variables that affect teachers' ability to fulfill the roles expected of them. However, teachers acquired these characteristics during their undergraduate period when they became practice teachers. Thus, since the teaching profession is considered a profession that requires specialized knowledge and skills, practice teachers should possess specific competencies, self-efficacy, and a professional attitude. Globally, research has shown that teacher education programs integrating theoretical instruction with practical classroom experience tend to develop graduates with stronger self-efficacy (Livers et al., 2020). These programs help aspiring educators connect academic concepts with real-life classroom applications, allowing them to practice lesson delivery, manage classrooms, and assess student learning in authentic settings (Boss Krauss, 2022). This practical exposure

enables teachers to refine their skills and build confidence in addressing the diverse needs of learners. As they encounter real teaching challenges, their competence increases, reinforcing their belief in their ability to handle the complex responsibilities of the teaching profession (Shkerina et al., 2020). Teachers with low self-efficacy have emerged as a concern for education leaders worldwide. Cherry (2020) reported that about 30% of teachers at Maulana Azad National Urdu University in India exhibited low self-efficacy, which was linked to weak classroom management, avoidance of challenging tasks, and lack of commitment to school activities. Henriksen et al. (2020) observed that these teachers often focused on adverse outcomes, perceived challenges as personal failures, and avoided situations outside their comfort zones. Woodcock et al. (2022) noted that such low self-efficacy could lead to a closed mindset, limiting openness to new teaching strategies and innovations that could improve student learning. International studies have also highlighted that teachers who can adapt the curriculum and apply differentiated strategies tend to report higher levels of self-efficacy, particularly in culturally diverse classrooms (Pazhayannur, 2022). Adaptability enables educators to meet the diverse needs of learners, fostering inclusive and engaging learning environments. Similarly, those who integrate technology into their lessons often express greater confidence in promoting active learning and achieving instructional goals (Taimalu Luik, 2019). These findings suggest that professional competence extends beyond traditional teaching skills, encompassing flexibility, creativity, and responsiveness to the evolving demands of modern education. In the Philippines, Fajardo et al. (2019) reported satisfactory levels of teaching efficacy in Cagayan de Oro City, with average scores of 3.11 and 3.22. They noted that teachers with low self-efficacy often relied heavily on textbooks, modules, and prescribed materials, limiting students' opportunities to develop critical thinking, creativity, and deeper understanding. Such beliefs, once formed, tend to persist in future classrooms. Similarly, Digal and Walag (2019) observed that low self-efficacy made teachers more likely to give up during setbacks, lack confidence in achieving their goals, and experience feelings of failure, thereby reducing their resilience in handling stressful situations. In addition to the Philippine context, research has consistently emphasized the importance of professional competence in strengthening teachers' confidence to perform their responsibilities effectively. Core elements such as mastery of subject matter, sound pedagogical skills, and effective classroom management have been identified as key contributors to this confidence (Padillo et al., 2021). Teachers who demonstrate higher competence often express greater assurance in their ability to motivate learners, sustain active participation, and foster a positive learning environment (Monteiro et al., 2021). These findings highlight that competence not only improves instructional quality but also reinforces self-belief in fulfilling diverse teaching roles successfully. Furthermore, research within the national setting also highlighted the role of professional development programs in boosting both competence and efficacy (Bantoc Yazon, 2023). Initiatives from the Department of Education have provided avenues for continuous improvement, enabling teachers to refine their teaching strategies and increase their confidence in achieving learning outcomes. Furthermore, competence in assessment and the ability to provide constructive feedback were found to be closely associated with a stronger belief in influencing student learning (Mendoza et al., 2023). By effectively measuring progress and adjusting lessons accordingly, teachers reinforced their perceptions of being effective practitioners. In the local setting, research in the Davao Region has demonstrated that professional competence has a strong influence on teachers' sense

of efficacy, particularly in classroom management and student engagement. Budo (2023) found that educators who actively participated in skills enhancement programs demonstrated higher confidence in handling diverse learning needs. Abendaño et al. (2023) emphasized that teachers in the region who adopted innovative and localized teaching strategies were more effective in sustaining student interest and performance. Competence was regarded as both a professional asset and a community expectation, as effective teaching was seen to contribute to the overall success of the school directly. Thus, in this context, the researcher needed to fill the research gap by conducting a study in the local setting, particularly in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher employed a descriptive-correlational design to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between professional competence and teacher self-efficacy, which was found to be scarce. Studying the relationship between professional competence and teacher self-efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, is important because it can help Philippine Journals or publications identify challenges in teachers' instructional practices, improve professional development programs to boost self-efficacy, and ultimately lead to better student outcomes. Research in the broader Davao Region reveals a connection between professional development, self-efficacy, and work values, suggesting that local studies can inform policies aimed at enhancing teaching quality and supporting teachers in high-workload environments. The present study aims to contribute to the limited body of knowledge regarding professional competence and teacher self-efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Professional Competence*—Professional competence refers to advanced knowledge, skills, and adaptability acquired through experience, continuous learning, and reflective

practice (Suphasri Chonokul, 2021; Graham et al., 2020). Expert teachers employ diverse strategies, adapt to student needs, diagnose learning gaps, and foster engagement (Anderson Taner, 2023; Phillipson Phillipson, 2020; Gess-Newsome et al., 2019). They also become mentors and leaders, guiding colleagues and improving school culture (Amerstorfer Munster-Kistner, 2021; Moats, 2020; Ventista Brown, 2023).

Studies show gender differences in competence: females score higher in planning, organizing, empathy, and coaching, while males excel in decision-making, management, and negotiation (Vincent Focht, 2020). Competence assessment remains complex due to varied skill definitions (Haleem et al., 2022; Christoforidou Kyriakides, 2021; Hargie, 2021).

Professional expertise enhances teacher efficacy, confidence, and instructional adaptability (Boone et al., 2020; Shavelson, 2020; Zahid Khanam, 2019). Reflective practice and continual development further strengthen teaching performance and resilience.

1.1.2. *Indicators of Competence*—Environmental Control: Expert teachers design supportive physical and social environments, maintain routines, and integrate technology effectively (Fitzgerald et al., 2022; Hanaysha et al., 2023; Cox, 2019; Akram et al., 2022).

Self-Disclosure: Appropriate sharing of experiences fosters trust, motivation, and inclusivity, while excessive disclosure is avoided (Masur, 2019; Mebert et al., 2019; Zhang, 2022; Bouhafa et al., 2023).

Assertiveness: Teachers communicate confidently and respectfully, building order and mutual respect, unlike unassertive counterparts who struggle with low self-esteem (Carstensen Klusmann, 2021; Utami et al., 2019; Paterson, 2022).

Interaction Management: Expert teachers manage classroom interactions to ensure engagement, inclusivity, and effective communica-

tion (Cline et al., 2022; Burden, 2020; Markey et al., 2021; Sjolie et al., 2021).

Immediacy: Warmth and responsiveness through verbal and nonverbal cues improve student engagement, behavior, and academic performance (Andersen, 2019; Zheng, 2021; Liu Geng, 2023).

1.1.3. Teachers' Sense of Efficacy—Teacher efficacy is the belief in one's ability to plan, organize, and execute effective teaching (Olave, 2019). It is linked to higher student achievement, openness to innovation, and improved classroom climate (Conroy et al., 2019; Zaky, 2020; Putwain von der Embse, 2019). High self-efficacy also supports resilience, reflective practice, and leadership roles (Li, 2023; Orsini Coers, 2022; Gordon et al., 2023). Teachers with strong efficacy report greater fulfillment and less burnout (Ballantyne Retell, 2020; Zepeda, 2019; Sears et al., 2021).

1.1.4. Indicators of Efficacy—Student Engagement: Self-efficacious teachers motivate students, foster positive climates, and adapt to diverse learning needs (Olivier et al., 2019; Zakariya, 2020; Kahu et al., 2021).

Instructional Strategies: High-efficacy teachers apply varied, student-centered approaches, set clear goals, and use formative assessments effectively (Ozdemir et al., 2020; Woodcock et al., 2022; Hudson, 2021).

Classroom Management: Teachers with strong efficacy maintain order, equity, and routines, fostering inclusivity and positive relationships, though average efficacy may limit consistency (Conroy et al., 2019; Aksoy, 2020; Bandura, 2023; Wilson et al., 2020).

1.2. Synthesis—Therefore, this section of the paper presents the researcher's discussion of the literature and the results of other studies related to or similar to the present study. Studies consistently highlight the interplay between professional expertise and teachers' sense of efficacy. Teachers with strong expertise in content knowledge, pedagogy, and experience tend

to have higher levels of self-efficacy. They engage in reflective practice, embrace professional development, and witness positive student outcomes. Additionally, a supportive school environment and the ability to overcome challenges contribute to their self-efficacy. These findings underscore the importance of investing in professional development and creating supportive school cultures to enhance both professional expertise and teacher efficacy, ultimately benefiting students and the overall quality of education. Professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy are crucial and positively related to teaching and learning development in areas like Asuncion, Davao del Norte, as evidenced by research in the Davao Region. Higher teacher competence and self-efficacy empower teachers to employ effective instructional strategies, fostering a dynamic and student-centered learning environment that directly contributes to improved student engagement and achievement. The interplay between competence and efficacy in teaching shows that mastering subject knowledge, teaching strategies, and classroom management boosts teachers' confidence (self-efficacy). In turn, a strong sense of efficacy encourages teachers to innovate, adapt to student needs, and adopt student-centered methods, resulting in improved learning outcomes. In Davao del Norte, teachers face challenges in instructional practices due to limited professional development opportunities, which can negatively impact their self-efficacy.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— This study is grounded in the proposition by Boone et al. (2020) that teachers with deep content knowledge are more confident in their ability to convey information and foster understanding among their students. When teachers are experts in their subject matter, they feel more capable of addressing students' questions and challenges, leading to increased self-efficacy. Proficient pedagogical skills enable teachers to employ effective instructional strategies and class-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

room management techniques. Expert teachers are more effective at planning engaging lessons, addressing diverse learning needs, and adapting their teaching methods, which leads to greater self-efficacy. In support, Shavelson (2020) illustrated that teachers who engage in ongoing professional development are more likely to increase their knowledge and skills. Continual learning and training can boost teachers' confidence in their ability to stay current with best practices and adapt to evolving educational trends. Likewise, Zahid and Khanam (2019) proposed that expert teachers engage in reflective practice, critically evaluating their teaching methods and outcomes. This self-reflection helps them identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments, ultimately enhancing their self-efficacy. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable of the study is professional competence, which refers to the outcome of a teacher's job and referencing skills that lead to superior performance. According to Werle and Byrd (2022) professional competence is measured in terms of environmental control or the process of

organizing and conducting the business of the classroom; self-disclosure or the act of revealing personal or private information about oneself to other people; assertiveness or the quality of being self-assured and confident without being aggressive to defend a correct point of view or a relevant statement; interaction management or the meaningful communication among the students in the classroom; and immediacy or the quality that makes something seem important or interesting. The dependent variable is teachers' sense of efficacy or the belief that they can have a positive effect on student learning. The measure of teachers' sense of efficacy according to Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk (2021) are student engagement or the degree or quality of students' participation and involvement in their learning process, both in and out of the classroom; instructional strategies or the methods that teachers use to deliver course material in ways that keep students engaged in learning; and classroom management or the wide variety of skills and techniques that teachers use to ensure that their classroom runs smoothly, without disruptive behavior from students.

1.4. Statement of the Problem —The primary aim of this study was to determine which among the domains of professional competence significantly influence teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of professional competence of the teachers in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division in terms of:

- (1) Environmental control;
 - (2) self-disclosure;
 - (3) assertiveness;
 - (4) Interaction Management
 - (5) immediacy?
- (2) What is the extent of teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, in terms of:
- (1) Student Engagement;
 - (2) Instructional strategies; and
 - (3) Classroom Management?
- (3) Is there a significant relationship between professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division?
- (4) Which among the domains of professional competence significantly influences teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division?

1.5. *Hypothesis*—The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance: H01 There is no significant relationship between professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. H02 None of the domain of professional competence significantly influence teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte Division. It is assumed that the study would also be beneficial to specific individuals and groups in the academe. Department of Education. The results generate facts that are important in developing teachers' sense of efficacy, which is known to be beneficial in providing quality education to students. Therefore, the findings of this study will serve as a basis for the Department of Education to propose guidelines for educational planners to create programs that improve the professional and personal well-being of elementary school teachers. Policy Makers. This study would benefit policymakers since the findings may bridge the methodological divide in teaching practices research by attempting to understand not only the self-efficacy of teachers but also the aspect of professional competence. Hence, this study provides a synthesis of both approaches. In addition, while research on the effects of professional competence on teachers' sense of efficacy

has to date focused mainly on a foreign context, this program of research builds on the established relationship between professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy among teachers in Davao del Norte. Teachers. The result would be beneficial to the teachers, as it generates facts that are important in providing a conducive working environment. Since it was already known that teachers' sense of efficacy has a significant impact on their performance and satisfaction, and is also an important component of educational and instructional processes, the findings of this study justify the importance of professional competence to the self-efficacy of teachers in their work. Therefore, the evidence gathered from this study will be helpful for teachers to develop a sense of efficacy in their work, considering their professional competence as teachers. Future Researchers. Other researchers would benefit from the results of this study, as the findings may provide a framework and model for future research on professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Professional Competence. In this study, the independent variable is described in terms of environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and im-

mediacy. Teachers' Self-Efficacy. In this study, the dependent variable is described in terms of the following indicators: student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management.

2. Methodology

This section details the methodology employed, encompassing the research design, participant selection, data collection instrument, data collection process, and subsequent data analysis, culminating in a discussion of the findings.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research technique to gather data, ideas, facts, and information related to the study. Bhandari (2020) described quantitative research as a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. It is formed from a deductive approach, where emphasis is placed on testing theories, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies. In contrast, non-experimental research is research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur in the real world. Meanwhile, descriptive correlational research, according to Stangor and Walinga (2019), is a study in which the researcher is primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. In this study, the researcher examined the professional competence and teachers' sense of efficacy in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. Specifically, the study focused on the relationships among variables to determine the significance of the relationship between the two variables. In this study, a descriptive-correlational approach was employed because the researcher focused solely on the behavioral aspect of the respondents, and no experiment was conducted in a controlled setting.

2.2. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the elementary school

teachers in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. In this study, the 185 respondents were selected through a stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In this study, specific inclusion criteria were used to determine the respondents. The primary consideration of this study was to select respondents who could provide the necessary information to achieve its purpose. Hence, only those permanent-regular elementary school teachers in Asuncion, Davao del Norte, who voluntarily signed the ICF were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions. Thus, it did not take into account the gender and socio-economic status of the teachers.

2.3. Research Instruments—The study employed questionnaires adapted from various studies and modified to fit the context of the respondents in this study. The instrument was divided into two parts. The first part of the instrument, adapted from Bugwak's (2022) study, was used to measure teachers' competence, which consists of five domains: environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all items in each dimension under their respective domains. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale, which is as follows: 5—Always, 4—Oftentimes, 3—Sometimes Agree,

2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Professional Competence, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The professional competence is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Professional competence is often observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The professional competence is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Professional competence is seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The professional competence is never observed.

Note. This table shows the descriptive interpretation of professional competence levels according to the range of mean scores.

The second part of the instrument was the Teachers’ Sense of Efficacy, adapted from Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk (2021), which is divided into three domains: efficacy in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. The researcher modified the questionnaire by grouping all items within each dimension under their respective domains. In answering the questionnaire, the respondents used the 5-Likert scale, which is as follows: 5–Always, 4–Oftentimes, 3–Sometimes Agree, 2–Seldom, 1–Never Disagree. As a guide in determining the level of Teachers’ Sense of Efficacy, the researcher made use of the range of means, description, and interpretation as presented below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ sense of efficacy is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ sense of efficacy is often manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ sense of efficacy is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ sense of efficacy is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ sense of efficacy is never manifested.

Note. This table shows the descriptive interpretation of the teachers’ sense of efficacy based on the range of mean scores.

The questionnaire was pilot-tested in a nearby school and obtained a Cronbach’s alpha value greater than 0.700, which ensured that the questionnaire had a high level of internal consistency. The scaling was performed by setting one-half of the value of 5 as the average cut-off point, or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Before administering the instrument, it was subject to validation by three experts, and revisions were made according to their expert comments.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure —The researcher took steps to conduct the study after validating the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, was attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public schools in Asuncion, Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to distribute the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. This was done on May 22-24, 2023. Upon distributing the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly

discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher distributed the questionnaires in accordance with health protocols. The participants in the study were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After retrieving the data from the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. Afterward, each score was subjected to both descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—The researcher promptly observed the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study, following the study protocol assessment criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires, along with supporting authors, were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study.

Social Value – Research significantly contributes to societal well-being. In this specific investigation, the primary focus was on exploring the experiences of educators, particularly those teaching at the elementary level. Moreover, the results aimed to assist policymakers and educational authorities in developing programs and policies that better support teachers. The central social concern driving this study was the exploration of professional competence as a key factor influencing teachers' sense of efficacy.

Informed Consent – The researcher obtained written informed consent from the respondents. They were thoroughly informed about the purpose of the study, and provided ample explanations to help them better understand the reasons for their participation, enabling them to make an informed decision about whether to take part

or not and made it clear that participation was voluntary and that they were not compelled to join if they chose not to. The researcher also took care to ensure the respondents' psychological well-being throughout the process. A written consent was secured from each participant and informed them that the study aimed to explore the factors that influence or hinder teaching behaviors in relation to teachers' professional quality of life and that the findings could contribute to potential improvements.

Vulnerability of Research Participants – The participants of the study were teachers, who were considered non-vulnerable because all of them were of legal age and not deemed highly vulnerable on a psychological level. The researcher emphasized that the survey was designed to be conducted at their convenience. Additionally, he maintained strict confidentiality regarding the information they disclosed. *Privacy and Confidentiality* – The study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, ensuring that the collected data could not be traced back to individual participants to protect their identities. The researcher also guaranteed that no personal data would be shared without the participants' consent. To safeguard their privacy, access to the data was limited solely to me. After collecting the necessary information, the researcher permanently deleted all online survey results to ensure they could not be linked back to the respondents.

Risk, Benefits, and Safety – When administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed the nature of their involvement and explained the purpose, benefits, and confidentiality measures of the study. Participants were encouraged to ask questions related to the study and were assured that they would not be subjected to any harm in any form. The questionnaires and interview guides used in the research did not contain any offensive, degrading, or inappropriate statements. The study was designed solely to gather academic information,

and no personal data were solicited. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher provided ample time for respondents to complete the on-line surveys. Participants were free to decline answering any questions that caused discomfort or distress, and could withdraw from the study at any time if they felt unable to share certain information, prioritized their welfare, and valued their participation throughout the research process.

Justice – To ensure impartiality in selecting respondents, the researcher treated all participants equally, regardless of whether they were part of the survey. Likewise, he did not discriminate in choosing the participants, selecting only those who met the criteria of being permanent-regular employees in the purposively selected schools. During data collection, the researcher was careful to minimize disruption to their routines. As a token of appreciation for their time, the researcher sent souvenirs via courier, carefully sealed and sanitized before delivery.

Transparency – To ensure transparency throughout this study, the researcher conducted all research-related communication with honesty and clarity. To protect the welfare of the participants, the researcher carefully implemented the methods outlined for this study. All relevant documents supporting the data analysis were included. Notably, the researcher described the extent of the respondents' involvement and explained how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing the data and presenting the results.

Qualifications of the Researcher – The researcher ensured that any external factors, such as conflicts of interest, did not influence the responses from participants. The findings were accessible to the respondents, their parents, and school administrators of the participating institutions, provided they adhered to proper protocols to ensure respondent anonymity and confidentiality. He also acknowledged the contributions of everyone who helped facilitate the study. A

comprehensive copy of the research results was shared with the Division of Davao del Norte for access by the respondents and use in learning and future research.

Adequacy of Facilities – The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment with sufficient learning materials, which were readily available throughout the study period. The research was conducted within the designated timeframe. To ensure the accuracy of data collection, the researcher meticulously encoded the respondents' ratings on days when they were less fatigued, thereby minimizing potential errors. The analysis and findings were consistent and aligned, serving as a primary basis for evaluating the adequacy of the facilities.

Community Involvement – The researcher recognized the importance of community participation at every stage of the research, from planning to reporting. Therefore, the researcher planned to share the findings with the community and prioritized their involvement in decision-making regarding the research agenda, the methods to be employed, and the application of the results. The study's outcomes were intended to be shared through community gatherings, forums, and conferences to foster engagement and collaborative understanding.

2.6. Data Analysis —The researcher employed several statistical tools to analyze the collected data. Firstly, the Mean was used to describe and interpret the levels of professional competence among teachers and their sense of efficacy, helping to address the first two research objectives. To examine the relationship between these variables, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation coefficient was utilized. This statistical measure assesses the strength and direction of the linear association between the independent variable, professional competence, and the dependent variable, teachers' sense of efficacy. The correlation coefficient, represented by 'r' in the analysis, provides insight into how closely these variables are related within the

sample. Also, Multiple Linear Regression analysis was conducted to determine the extent to which professional competence predicts or influences teachers’ sense of efficacy. This method evaluates the significance and impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable, offering a more comprehensive understanding of their relationship.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study’s objectives, as explained in Chapter 1. Thus, it presents the extents of professional competence and teachers’ sense of efficacy in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; the significant relationship between professional competence and teachers’ sense of efficacy in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte; and the influence of professional competence on the teachers’ sense of efficacy in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte.

3.1. Professional Competence of Teachers—

3.1.1. *Environmental Control*—Table 1 shows that the professional competence of teachers in terms of environmental control was assessed by the respondents as extensive, with a category mean of 3.66, indicating that this is often observed by teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.24 to 4.09. On the other hand, the item ‘Persuading others to my position’ has a mean rating of 3.24, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. On the other

hand, the item It is challenging to find the right words to express myself reflects a mean of 4.09, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed by the teachers. This means that teachers’ ability to manage and manipulate the physical, social, and emotional classroom environment to optimize teaching and learning is often observed. This is consistent with Hanaysha et al. (2023), who view that teachers with high levels of professional expertise have a deep understanding of how environmental factors impact the educational experience and can effectively adjust these elements to enhance student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes.

Table 1. Professional Competence in Terms of Environmental Control

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. It is difficult to find the right words to express myself.	4.09	Extensive
2. Accomplish my communication goals.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
3. Persuading others to my position.	3.24	Moderately Extensive
4. Expressing myself well verbally.	3.97	Extensive
Mean	3.66	Extensive

Note. This table presents the professional competence of individuals in terms of environmental control, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

3.1.2. *Self-Disclosure*—Table 2 shows that the professional competence of teachers in terms of self-disclosure was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean

of 3.63, interpreted as oftentimes observed by the teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.22 to 4.03. The item Reveal-

ing how I feel to others has a mean rating of 3.22, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. Meanwhile, the item Other people think that I understand them reflects a mean of 4.03, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed. This implies that teachers can judiciously use self-disclosure as an instructional tool to enhance the learning experience for students. The result is in agreement to Masur’s (2019) view that when teachers self-disclose ap-

propriately, it can foster stronger and more trusting relationships with students. This can lead to improved communication and support for academic and personal growth. Self-disclosure can make lessons more relevant and authentic. Moreover, the result is similar to the idea of Henry and Thorsen (2021) that appropriately timed self-disclosure can capture students’ attention and spark their interest in the subject matter. Personal stories can be engaging and motivating.

Table 2. Professional Competence in Terms of Self-Disclosure

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Others would describe me as warm.	3.84	Extensive
2. Revealing how I feel to others.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
3. Telling people when I feel close to them.	3.44	Extensive
4. Other people think that I understand them.	4.03	Extensive
Mean	3.63	Extensive

Note. This table presents the professional competence of individuals in terms of self-disclosure, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

3.1.3. *Assertiveness*—Table 3 shows that the professional competence of teachers in terms of assertiveness was rated by the teachers as extensive with a category mean of 3.45, interpreted as oftentimes observed by the elementary school teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.01 to 4.12. The item Taking charge of conversations I’m in by negotiating what topics we talk about has a mean rating of 3.01, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. Whereas, the item Confronting the person who wronged me when I have been wronged shows a mean of 4.12, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed by the respondents. This means that teachers can

assert themselves effectively to create a positive and productive learning environment, manage classroom dynamics, and advocate for the best interests of their students and themselves. This view is similar to that of Utami et al. (2019), who assert that assertive teachers can establish and maintain clear and consistent rules and expectations, resulting in better classroom discipline and order. High expertise enables teachers to assert themselves without being aggressive or confrontational. They can maintain a respectful and empathetic tone when addressing students, parents, and colleagues. Kanade (2019) proposed that assertiveness helps build positive teacher-student relationships based on mutual respect. Students know what is expected, and teachers can advocate for their needs.

3.1.4. *Interaction Management* —Table 4 shows that the professional competence of teachers in terms of interaction management

was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean of 3.42, interpreted as oftentimes observed by the teachers in Talain-

Table 3. Professional Competence in Terms of Assertiveness

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Confronting the person who wronged me when I have been wronged.	4.12	Extensive
2. Taking charge of conversations I'm in by negotiating what topics we talk about.	3.01	Moderately Extensive
3. Having trouble standing up for myself.	3.58	Extensive
4. Standing up for my rights.	3.10	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.45	Extensive

Note. This table presents the professional competence of individuals in terms of assertiveness, with mean scores and descriptive ratings. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.99 to 3.81. On one hand, the item Effective interaction management is fundamental in improving teachers' professional expertise has a mean rating of 2.99, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. On the other hand, the item Letting my learners know that I understand what they say reflects a mean of 3.81, described as extensive and interpreted as often observed by the teachers. The results suggest that educators often demonstrate the ability to plan, facilitate, and manage interactions within the classroom or educational setting effectively. This is congruent with Franklin and Harrington's (2019) assertion that expert teachers create a well-managed and positive classroom environment that is conducive to learning, promoting active student engagement and participation. They manage interactions to provide individualized support to students based on their diverse needs, learning styles, and abilities.

Table 4. Professional Competence in Terms of Interaction Management

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Letting my learners know that I understand what they say.	3.81	Extensive
2. Perceiving not only what they say but also what they do not say in conversations with my learners.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
3. Effective interaction management fundamental in improving teachers' professional expertise.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
4. Effective communication a key component influencing teachers' professional expertise.	3.67	Extensive
Mean	3.42	Extensive

Note. This table presents the professional competence of individuals in terms of interaction management, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

3.1.5. *Immediacy*—Table 5 shows that the professional competence of teachers in terms of immediacy was assessed by the respondents as extensive with a category mean of 3.32, interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.99 to 3.82. On one hand, the item Being good at organizing information has a mean rating of 2.99, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the respondents. On the other hand, the item Understanding my intellectual strengths and weaknesses reflects a mean of 3.82, described as extensive and interpreted

as often observed by the teachers.

Table 5. Professional Competence in Terms of Immediacy

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Allowing learners to see who I really am.	3.34	Moderately Extensive
2. My learners truly believe that I care about them.	3.82	Extensive
3. Trying to look others in the eye when I speak with them.	3.12	Moderately Extensive
4. Immediate feedback provided by teachers a crucial factor in enhancing professional expertise.	2.99	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

Note. This table presents the professional competence of individuals in terms of immediacy, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

This implies that teachers possess some ability to establish immediacy in their teaching, but they may not consistently or fully employ these behaviors. This supports the findings of Zheng (2021) that teachers with moderate immediacy can foster positive relationships with students, helping to create a supportive and respectful learning environment. This also supports the idea of Liu and Geng (2023) that moderate immediacy behaviors can lead to an emotional connection between teachers and students, helping to create a supportive and nurturing classroom atmosphere. A classroom with moderate immediacy is likely to have a more positive and welcoming climate, which can promote better student behavior and interactions. Lastly, Table 6 shows the summary on professional expertise of teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. It shows that the overall mean of students' self-perceptive awareness is 3.50 which is described as extensive. It means that the professional expertise of teachers is oftentimes observed. More so, professional competence in terms of environmental control acquired the highest mean score of 3.66, described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes observed, while professional com-

petence in terms of immediacy acquired the lowest mean score of 3.32, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed by the teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This implies that the advanced level of knowledge, skills, and competencies that educators acquire through years of experience, continuous learning, and reflective practice in their teaching careers is often observed. The result is in agreement with the proposition of Van Geel et al. (2023) that expert teachers are adept at employing a wide range of effective teaching strategies tailored to the needs of their students. They can adapt their methods to different learning styles and abilities. They can individualize instruction, catering to the unique needs and abilities of each student. More so, the result reflects similarity with Ellis et al.'s (2019) findings that expert teachers are often at the forefront of educational innovation. They can develop and experiment with creative approaches to teaching and learning. Expertise allows teachers to create engaging and meaningful learning experiences. They can motivate students, foster curiosity, and sustain their interest in learning.

3.2. *Sense of Efficacy of Teachers*—

3.2.1. *Student Engagement* —Table 7 shows that the sense of efficacy of teachers

in terms of student engagement was described by the elementary school teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, as extensive, with

Table 6. Summary on Teachers’ Professional Competence in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Environmental Control	3.66	Extensive
Self-Disclosure	3.63	Extensive
Assertiveness	3.45	Extensive
Interaction Management	3.42	Extensive
Immediacy	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.50	Extensive

Note. This table summarizes the teachers’ professional competence across different indicators in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, with mean scores and descriptive equivalents.

a category mean of 3.55. This means that the sense of efficacy of teachers is oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.09 to 4.12. The item Helping to assist my learners’ families in helping their children to do well in school shows a mean rating of 3.09, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item is sometimes observed. Further, the item Inspiring my learners to believe in themselves that they can do well in school work has a mean rating of 4.12, described as extensive and interpreted as this item often manifests. This implies the extent to which students are actively involved in the learning process, motivated, and attentive in the classroom is often manifested. This is similar

to the findings of Hu et al. (2019) that high teacher efficacy contributes to a positive and supportive classroom environment. When students feel that their teacher is in control and capable, they are more comfortable and engaged in the learning process. Adding more, this result supports Zaky’s (2020) proposition that teachers with high efficacy can inspire and motivate students to become more engaged in their learning. When students perceive their teachers as confident and capable, they are more likely to approach their studies with enthusiasm. Students are more likely to actively participate in classroom activities, discussions, and assignments when they believe their teacher can guide them effectively.

Table 7. Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Terms of Student Engagement

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Motivating learners who show low interest in school work.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
2. Inspiring my learners to believe in themselves that they can do well in school work.	4.12	Extensive
3. Helping my learners value learning.	3.88	Extensive
4. Helping to assist my learners’ families in helping their children to do well in school.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.55	Extensive

Note. This table presents the teachers’ sense of efficacy in terms of student engagement, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

3.2.2. *Instructional Strategies* —Table 8 shows that sense of efficacy of teachers in terms

instructional strategies was described by the elementary school teachers as extensive with a cate-

gory mean of 3.42. This means that the sense of efficacy of teachers are oftentimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 3.13 to 4.02. The item Crafting good questions for my learners shows a mean rating of 3.13, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item sometimes observed by the students. Further, the item Using a variety of assessment strategies has a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested. This implies that the methods and approaches that educators employ to facilitate learning and instruction in the classroom is oftentimes manifested

in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This is similar to Ojong’s (2023) idea that teachers with high efficacy are more likely to use a wide range of instructional strategies, tailoring their approach to suit different learning styles and abilities within the classroom. They encourage the exploration and application of innovative instructional techniques that can make learning more engaging and effective. Instructional strategies associated with active student participation and engagement, such as group discussions, problem-solving activities, and hands-on projects, are more prevalent in the classroom of teachers with high efficacy.

Table 8. Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Terms of Instructional Strategies

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Crafting good questions for my learners.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
2. Using a variety of assessment strategies.	4.02	Extensive
3. Providing an alternative explanation or example when learners are confused.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
4. Implementing alternative strategies in my classroom.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.42	Extensive

Note. This table presents the teachers’ sense of efficacy in terms of instructional strategies, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

3.2.3. *Classroom Management*—Table 9 shows that sense of efficacy of teachers in terms classroom management was described by the elementary school teachers as moderately extensive with a category mean of 3.28. This means that the sense of efficacy of teachers are sometimes manifested. The mean rating of the different items ranges from 2.89 to 4.02. The item Calming my learner who is disruptive or noisy shows a mean rating of 2.89, described as moderately extensive and interpreted as this item sometimes observed by the students. Further, the item Getting children to follow classroom rules has a mean rating of 4.02, described as extensive and interpreted as this item oftentimes manifested in Asuncion Dis-

trict, Davao del Norte. This implies the strategies and techniques educators use to establish and maintain order, discipline, and a positive learning environment within the classroom is sometimes manifested. This is congruent to Conroy et al., (2019) proposition that teachers with average efficacy are likely to establish and enforce consistent classroom rules and expectations. While they may not be as confident as highly efficacious teachers, they still maintain order and structure. Moreover, this is congruent with Rusu’s (2021) idea that teachers with average efficacy aim for clear and effective communication with students. They may encounter challenges in managing behavior due to their moderate sense of efficacy.

Table 9. Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Terms of Classroom Management

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Controlling disruptive behavior in the classroom.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
2. Getting children to follow classroom rules.	4.02	Extensive
3. Calming my learner who is disruptive or noisy.	2.89	Moderately Extensive
4. Establishing a classroom management system with each group of learners.	2.98	Extensive
Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

Note. This table presents the teachers’ sense of efficacy in terms of classroom management, with mean scores and descriptive ratings.

Lastly, as shown in Table 10, is the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. As shown in the table, the sense of efficacy of teachers obtained an overall mean score of 3.42 with a descriptive rating of extensive and interpreted as often manifested by the teachers. Adding more, results on Table 10 show that sense of efficacy of teachers in terms of student engagement acquired the highest mean score of 3.55 described as extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested, while, sense of efficacy of teachers in terms of classroom management got the lowest mean score of 3.28 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested by the elementary school teachers. The results indicate that teachers’ belief in their own capability to plan, organize, and execute instructional

strategies effectively to facilitate student learning is often evident among teachers in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This supports the idea of Conroy et al., (2019) that teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to design and implement effective instructional practices. They have confidence in their ability to teach and engage students in learning. High self-efficacy is linked to improved student achievement. Teachers who believe in their capacity to make a difference can motivate and inspire their students to excel academically. Adding more, this supports Majer’s (2019) assertion that teachers with high self-efficacy are better at solving instructional challenges. They are more likely to persist in finding solutions to obstacles that may arise in the teaching-learning process.

Table 10. Summary on Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Student Engagement	3.55	Extensive
Instructional Strategies	3.42	Extensive
Classroom Management	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.42	Extensive

Note. This table summarizes the sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, with mean scores and descriptive equivalents.

3.3. *Relationship Between Professional Competence and Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte*—The re-

sults of the analysis of the relationship between professional competence and sense of efficacy among teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao

del Norte, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson product-moment correlation, was employed to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 11 shows that professional competence has a significant positive relationship with the sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte, with a p-value of .000 that is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.667, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of professional competence changes, the sense of efficacy of teachers also changes

significantly. Adding more, results on the table shows that professional expertise in terms of environmental control; self-disclosure; assertiveness; interaction management; and immediacy have significant positive relationship with the sense of efficacy of elementary school teachers in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.506, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.454, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.233, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.550, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.335, p < 0.05$), respectively.

Table 11. Relationship Between Professional Competence and Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Environmental Control	0.506*	0.000	Reject H0
Self-Disclosure	0.454*	0.000	Reject H0
Assertiveness	0.233*	0.001	Reject H0
Interaction Management	0.550*	0.000	Reject H0
Immediacy	0.335*	0.001	Reject H0
Overall Professional Competence	0.667*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Note. This table presents the relationship between professional competence and sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, with r-values, p-values, and the decisions made based on statistical significance.

The result implies that as teachers continually develop their professional expertise, they are likely to see an improvement in their sense of efficacy, which, in turn, positively impacts their teaching and the overall educational experience for students. This is similar to Zahid and Khanam’s (2019) proposition that expert teachers engage in reflective practice, critically evaluating their teaching methods and outcomes. This self-reflection helps them identify areas for improvement and make necessary adjustments, ultimately enhancing their self-efficacy.

3.4. *Influence of Professional Competence on the Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte* —The significance of the influence of professional competence on teachers’ sense of efficacy in the Asuncion Dis-

trict, Davao del Norte, was analyzed using linear regression analysis. Table 12 shows that when professional expertise, in terms of environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy, is considered as a predictor of teachers’ sense of efficacy, the model is significant, as evidenced by an F-value of 126.091 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that professional expertise predicts the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R-squared value of 0.442 indicates that professional competence has contributed significantly to the variability in the sense of efficacy of teachers, accounting for 44.20%. In addition, the table shows that there are domains of professional competence

that significantly influence the sense of efficacy among teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This table also indicates that professional competence, in terms of environmental control and self-disclosure, is a significant predictor of teachers' sense of efficacy in the Asuncion District of Davao del Norte. This means that the extent of teachers' sense of efficacy increases by 0.162 and 0.293 for each unit increase in professional competence. Thus, this leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis that none of the domains of professional competence significantly influence the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. This affirmed that teachers' sense of efficacy is a function of professional competence. This corroborates Shavelson's (2020) idea that teachers who engage in ongoing professional development are more likely to increase their knowledge and skills. Continual learning and

training can boost teachers' confidence in their ability to stay current with best practices and adapt to evolving educational trends. Adding more, the result is in agreement with Boone et al. (2020)'s view that teachers with deep content knowledge are more confident in their ability to convey information and foster understanding among their students. When teachers are experts in their subject matter, they feel more capable of addressing students' questions and challenges, leading to increased self-efficacy. According to Kibici (2022), and Koyuncuoğlu (2021), individuals with high levels of positive self-efficacy are more likely to persevere when faced with new and challenging tasks and to stay committed to completing them. Conversely, those who harbor negative self-efficacy beliefs tend to lack motivation, which can lead to abandoning tasks before finishing them.

Table 12. Influence of Professional Competence on the Sense of Efficacy of Teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte

Professional Competence	B	Beta	S.E	p-value	Decisions
Environmental Control	.162*	.233	.044	.000	Reject H0
Self-Disclosure	.293*	.406	.045	.000	Reject H0
Assertiveness	.093	.106	.048	.081	Accept H0
Interaction Management	-.088	.207	.034	.099	Accept H0
Immediacy	-.087	.107	.056	.101	Accept H0
R²		0.442			
F-value		126.091*			
p-value		0.000			

*Significant @ p<0.05

Note. This table presents the influence of professional competence on the sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, including B, Beta, Standard Error (S.E), p-value, and decisions made based on statistical significance.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the researcher's conclusions and recommendations. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion aligns with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate which domains of professional competence significantly influence teachers' sense of efficacy, utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 185 elementary school teachers from the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte as respondents using a stratified random sampling method. The researcher utilized modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument's items. The professional competence of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte had an overall mean of 3.50 with extensive descriptive ratings. Additionally, the professional competence of teachers in terms of environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, interaction management, and immediacy yielded mean scores of 3.66, 3.63, 3.45, 3.42, and 3.32, respectively. The sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte has an overall mean of 3.42 with an extensive descriptive rating. Also, sense of efficacy of teachers in terms of student engagement; instructional strategies; and classroom management obtained the mean scores 3.55, 3.42, and 3.28, respectively. The result showed that professional competence has a significant positive relationship with the sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte, with a p-value of .000, which is less than the .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .667$, $p < 0.05$). Professional competence in terms of environmental control and self-disclosure significantly influenced the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte, as evidenced by the F-value of 126.091 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.442 indicated that professional competence has contributed significantly to the variability of sense of efficacy of teachers in Asuncion District in Davao del Norte by 44.20

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: The extent of professional competence of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte was extensive. Meanwhile, the professional competence of teachers in terms of environmental control, self-disclosure, assertiveness, and interaction management obtained extensive descriptive ratings. In contrast, the professional expertise of teachers in terms of immediacy was rated as moderately extensive. The sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte, was rated as moderately extensive. The sense of efficacy of teachers in terms of student engagement and instructional strategies received an extensive rating. In contrast, the sense of efficacy of teachers in terms of classroom management received a moderately extensive rating. The results showed that professional competence has a significant positive relationship with the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This means that as the extent of professional competence changes, the sense of efficacy among teachers also changes significantly. This implies that the knowledge, skills, experience, and supportive factors associated with professional expertise contribute to teachers' self-confidence in their ability to teach effectively. Professional competence in terms of environmental control and self-disclosure are the domains that significantly influence the sense of efficacy of teachers in the Asuncion District, Davao del Norte. This affirmed that sense of efficacy is a function of professional competence of teachers in the Asuncion District in Davao del Norte. The relationship between professional competence (specifically deep content knowledge) and teachers' sense of efficacy is supported by the proposition that teachers with strong subject matter mastery are more confident in their ability to teach, convey information, and foster student understanding, according to studies building on this idea and research cited by Boone et al. (2020).

Deep content knowledge is a crucial component of professional competence that directly influences a teacher's self-belief in their teaching effectiveness, which is the essence of self-efficacy. Teachers with strong subject knowledge feel more confident in explaining concepts and engaging students, which improves their ability to facilitate learning. Content knowledge is a key part of their professional competence and influences their classroom interactions. This competence boosts teacher self-efficacy—the belief in their ability to manage and support student learning—by providing a solid foundation of knowledge and confidence to teach effectively.

4.3. *Recommendations*—The researcher recommends that the Department of Education (DepEd) allocate resources for ongoing, high-quality professional development programs that cater to the specific needs of teachers. These programs should focus on content knowledge, pedagogical skills, and classroom management. Also, DepEd should implement mentorship programs and encourage peer collaboration. Experienced teachers can support newer colleagues

by sharing their expertise and best practices.. School heads should establish regular feedback mechanisms to help teachers identify areas for improvement and growth. Use feedback to support targeted professional development. They should also recognize the importance of teacher well-being. Implement strategies to reduce teacher stress and burnout, such as providing mental health resources and implementing effective workload management. Teachers should engage in regular self-reflection on their teaching methods and their impact on student learning. Consider what areas of professional expertise can be strengthened. More so, teachers should advocate for the support and resources they need to enhance their professional expertise. Communicate with school leaders and policy makers about their professional development requirements. Future researchers should disseminate research findings to inform policy and practice. Make research accessible to educators, administrators, and policy makers to support evidence-based decision-making.

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